

Effect of Foundation Fixity on Buildings on Hill Slopes Under Earthquake Shaking

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Abstract Buildings located on hill slopes often encountered huge damages from past earthquakes due to their irregularity in elevation and plan. Building code provisions do not specify any separate design guidelines for these buildings except by limiting the height for estimating natural periods; this ensures stiffer and stronger buildings. Sometimes, landslides are accompanied by earthquake effects or due to heavy rains. The boundary conditions of these building changes suddenly (*e.g.*, fixed to roller) leading to catastrophic damage. Therefore, this study aims to identify the behaviour of buildings on hill slopes designed based on existing code provisions with fixed boundary conditions and assess its performance by suddenly varying the boundary conditions (*e.g.*, pinned or roller). Four different type of building configurations studied includes (a) building on plain ground, (b) step-back building, (c) step-back setback building and (d) step-back building on steep slope. The masonry walls are modelled as an equivalent strut. Elastic and inelastic behaviour of these buildings are obtained using Equivalent Static (ES), Response Spectrum (RS), Nonlinear Static (NLPoA) and Nonlinear Time History (NLTHA) Analyses. Based on the stress resultants, elastic and inelastic storey drifts, and level of damages in structural elements, the change in boundary conditions of buildings causes unusual behaviour or sometimes collapse without any warning. Also, change in fixity causes poor energy dissipation in step-back building, and with acceptable level of damages in other buildings on slopes. Step-back setback building performed better than other configurations. Therefore, code provisions must consider placing an additional provision including the effect of foundation fixity for buildings on hill slopes. It may be validated through building models considering soil-structure interactions.

Keywords Hill buildings, Boundary condition and Stiffness irregularity

Introduction

In civil engineering, it is crucial to thoroughly understand the behaviour of buildings located on hill slopes (like Himalayan regions) to withstand the the effect of landslides induced due to seismic activity or heavy rainfall. The combination of saturated slopes, substantial layers of alluvial deposits on extensively fractured bedrock, and the influence of tectonic activity and human involvement contribute to frequent slope failures in the hilly areas (Virdi et. al., 1995). It is essential to strengthen the structural integrity and long-term viability of buildings. Constructions in hilly regions undergo significant increases in shear force and torsional effects, principally caused by the anomalies in column heights resulting from seismic activity (Dimri and Kumar, 2022). In the event of a landslide center of mass and resistance is compromised due to sudden variation in stiffness along the horizontal and vertical axes. The dynamic characteristics of such buildings significantly differ from those on flat terrain. Earthquakes in the Indian Himalayan area have caused significant loss of human life and severe economic consequences. In the Indian hilly regions considerable number of buildings located on sloping terrains utilize a step-back architectural layout (Fig. 2b) or a step-back configuration particularly designed for steep slopes (Fig. 2d). These buildings employ multitiered foundations to adapt to the uneven topography (Surana et. al., 2018). After the 2011 Sikkim and the 2015 Nepal Earthquakes in the Indian-Himalayan region, which caused significant loss of life and damage to infrastructure, experts in the field have recognized that even with careful planning and the use of reinforced concrete (RC), buildings on slopes still experienced significant structural damage (Murty et. al., 2012; Sharma et. al., 2012; Varum et. al., 2018). The 2015 Nepal Earthquake, registering at a magnitude of 7.8, resulted in approximately 5,000,000 buildings damage and 30,000 fatalities. Failure of slope stability causes landslide which could leads to complete loss of building support failure (*e.g.*, one side of a building lost its support condition entirely due to failure in slope, Fig. 1a (Buchanan and Moroder, 2017)) while sometimes the building could move down slope due to failure of all of its supports (*e.g.*, various houses in the Army area sustained damage following a landslide that descended approximately 30 feet from the crown, Fig. 1b (Sharma et. al., 2015)). The latest provision of IS1893-1 restricts the height of the building while calculating its natural period which is used in equivalent static analysis. This implicitly ignores the type of building configuration or changes in boundary conditions that could affect the performance of building in the event of an earthquake. Hence, it is required to identify the critical parameters influencing the response of buildings on slopes and check the applicability of code provisions considering the effect of infill walls. In this study a set of 2D moment frame building configurations are modelled in ETABS software, base shear from response spectrum analysis is scaled to match equivalent static analysis. The selected buildings (such as BC1, BC2, BC3 and BC4, Fig. 2) are designed and checked for the applicability of provisions given in IS 1893-1 by varying the boundary conditions using nonlinear static and dynamic analyses using Perform 3D software. ETABS is used for elastic analysis, whereas Perform 3D is used for inelastic analysis, as the

nonlinear properties of structural elements are well defined.

Fig. 1. Failure of buildings on slope due to landslide: (a) corner foundation of building lost support due to slope stability failure (Buchanan and Moroder, 2017) and (b) damage of different houses on slope due to land slide (Sharma et. al., 2015).

Building Characteristics

Table 1 Cross-sectional properties and effective stiffnesses of beams and columns

Building Configurations	Cross-sections		Effective Stiffness	
	Beam (mm ²)	Column (mm ²)	Beam	Column
BC1	300 x 400	500 x 500	0.4	0.7
BC2, BC3, BC4, BC2 1R3H, BC2 2R, BC2 3R, BC2 3H, BC3 1R3H, BC3 2R, BC3 3R, BC2 3H BC2 1R3H, BC2 2R, BC2 3R, BC2 3H	300 x 400	400 x 400	0.4	0.7

Fig 2. Details of all building configurations (in m) (a) BC1, (b) BC2, (c) BC3 and (d) BC4

Elastic Behaviour

The modal mass participation ratio from the first five modes, natural period obtained of the first fundamental mode from ETABS and that calculated based on code-based expression is given in Table 3. For building on uniform ground greater than 80% mass participation is achieved whereas it reduces for buildings on slope depending upon the type of configuration ranging between 54% to 72%. Thus, it is necessary to design buildings based on response spectrum analysis considering $\geq 90\%$ mass participation ratio accounting a larger number of modes. Natural period calculated from code-based expression of regular building BC1 is almost near to the value estimated from ETABS while for other irregular buildings natural period estimated from ETABS is (~ 1.9 to 2.4 times) less than code calculated natural period. To address the irregular buildings, it is necessary to propose separate natural period expressions that account for their irregularities. To avoid disparity in this study natural period is calculated based on code-based expression considering shortest height for buildings on slope.

Table 2. Details of building configurations

S.No.	Description of buildings	Notation	S.No.	Description of buildings	Notation
1.	Building on Plain ground	BC1	9.	BC3 with 1 roller support at (A) and 2 hinge supports at (B & C)	BC31R2H
2.	Step-back building	BC2	10.	BC3 with 2 roller supports at (A & B)	BC3 2R
3.	Step-back setback building	BC3	11.	BC3 with 3 roller supports at (A, B & C)	BC3 3R
4.	Step-back building on steep slope	BC4	12.	BC3 with 3 hinge supports at (A, B & C)	BC3 3H
5.	BC2 with 1 roller support at (A) and 2 hinge supports at (B & C)	BC21R2H	13.	BC4 with 1 roller support at (A) and 2 hinge supports at (B & C)	BC41R2H
6.	BC2 with 2 roller supports at (A & B)	BC2 2R	14.	BC4 with 2 roller supports at (A & B)	BC4 2R
7.	BC2 with 3 roller supports at (A, B & C)	BC2 3R	15.	BC4 with 3 roller supports at (A, B & C)	BC4 3R
8.	BC2 with 3 hinge supports at (A, B & C)	BC2 3H	16.	BC4 with 3 hinge supports at (A, B & C)	BC4 3H

Table 3. Modal mass participation ratios and natural periods

Building Configurations	Modal participation ratio (%)					Natural period (s)		Base Shear (kN)
	Mode Numbers					ETABS	IS 1893-1	
	1	2	3	4	5			
BC1	85.98	9.93	2.76	1.03	0.3	0.29	0.33	207.76
BC2	72.24	11.06	6.4	7.47	2.55	0.14	0.27	173.49
BC3	54.77	14.28	8.87	17.58	4.01	0.11	0.27	112.15
BC4	67.04	26.52	1.82	0.95	3.67	0.10	0.20	152.80

Inelastic Behaviour

All buildings are designed and detailed as per IS 456 and IS 13920. Columns are modelled as spread plasticity model, core encompassed by transverse reinforcement is regarded as confined concrete (Mander et. al., 1988). The outer layer of cover concrete is depicted in the model with a failure strain limit of 0.0035. Beams are modelled as point plasticity model using a bilinear moment-curvature curve, where critical points represent the onset of steel yielding and concrete crushing (Sunita et. al., 2016). Columns are model as concrete and steel fibers, employing an idealized bilinear curve. The collapse criterion is set when the extreme confined concrete layer within a column reaches its limit state under bending compression. P-Δ effects are excluded, while including flexural deformation properties. All structural components adhere to the principles of kinematic hysteresis on elastoplastic backbone curves, maintaining their stiffness and strength without loss. Nonlinear static analysis was conducted to validate a 2D RC frame model (Vecchio and Emara, 1992) using Perform 3D software; initial stiffness showed a variation of 4.55%, failure strain 4.25% and peak strength 7%. Infill wall is idealized as a bilinear curve and the inelastic properties are calculated (Panagiotakos and Fardis, 1996). Subsequently, the structural struts were modeled with inelastic fibers, affixed centrally with both ends pinned to the frame elements. The onset of damage in the building is indicated by the yielding of struts, followed by subsequent damages in beams and columns, culminating in the ultimate failure of these structural elements. Structural elements are deemed damaged when their strain reaches or exceeds 80% of yielding, and they are considered completely compromised when their strain or curvature surpasses 80% of the ultimate limit state.

Nonlinear Static Analysis

To gain insights into the performance of buildings situated on slopes, a nonlinear static or pushover analysis (NLPoA) is conducted for all the building configurations. Capacity curves are obtained showcasing normalized base shear (V/W) and maximum inelastic drift at the center of mass (Δ_{CM} in %), as shown in Fig 3. Since the moment-curvature or confined concrete properties are idealized as a bilinear curve without accounting for strength and stiffness degradation, no strength degradation is noticed. The performance point (PP) is determined at the maximum considered earthquake (MCE) as per ATC-40 guidelines. A comprehensive comparative analysis of these buildings encompasses (i) the capacity curve, (ii) damage assessment in beams, columns, and struts at the PP, and (iii) elucidation of the damage

mechanisms at the PP (Fig. 4). Percentage of beams, columns, and struts yielding or ultimate failure is derived based on the total count of these structural elements (Table 4). Key observations gleaned from the NLPoA (Figs. 3 and 4, Table 4):

- (a) BC1 is having more strength compared to BC2, BC3, and BC4 (~10.6%, 5.6% and 10.5% lesser than BC1). Almost greater than 2% lateral drift is mobilized in all the buildings except (BC21R2H, BC2 2R and BC2 3R).
- (b) Drift of BC2 3R is least with poor energy dissipation capacity compared to all other building configurations. Also, the capacity of BC2 1R2H is less compared to BC3 1R2H and BC4 1R2H. Overall the BC2 buildings are not safe in the event of an earthquake in hilly regions. BC3 3H is having more lateral strength than all other buildings.
- (c) For the buildings with changes in boundary condition at PP, yielding in beams ranges between 22% to 66% with no failure in beams in most of the building except BC 2 3R and BC3 3R which are having 11% and 16% failure of beams. BC2, BC3 1R2H, BC32R and BC3 3H are having 0 % yielding of columns, while all other buildings evidenced yielding in columns of about 6% to 33%; however, there is no failure in columns in any of the buildings.
- (d) BC2 and BC3 buildings are having similar natural period however the damages in the beams, column and struts varies in all the buildings of the same configuration.

Nonlinear Dynamic

Seven far-field ground motions (GM) of magnitudes ranging from M6.3 to M7.3, with epicentral distances of 20 km to 50 km are scaled linearly to match the response spectrum of IS1893-1 for the maximum considered earthquake (MSE), Fig. 5 (Huang et. al., 2011; Reyes and Kalkan 2014). It is applied in X-direction considering that the buildings are designed based on code-specified natural periods. These GM are Niland Fire Station (GM1), Northridge-Downey-Co. Maint Bldg (GM2), San Fernando – Whittier Narrows Dam (GM3), San Fernando – LA – Hollywood Stor Lot (GM4), Superstition Hills (A) – Wildlife Liquef. Array (GM5), Kobe – Kakogawa (GM6), and Kobe – Sakai (GM7). The maximum inelastic drift (Δ_{CM}) is computed across all ground motions, and the mean value is integrated into the capacity curve derived from the NLPoA (Fig. 3). Percentage of damage incurred in beams, columns, and struts under NLTHA, considering yielding and ultimate limit states, is summarized in Table 4; finally, the damage mechanism of BC2 buildings for GM3 is shown in (Fig. 6). Key observations gleaned from the NLTHA (Figs. 3 and 6, Table 4):

Fig. 3. Comparison of capacity curve estimated from NLPoA for all building configurations including performance point.

Fig 4. (a) Damages in beams and columns due to yielding at PP; (b) ultimate failure of beams and columns at PP

Table 4. Percentage of yielding and ultimate failure of structural elements

Building Configurations	Analysis											
	NLPoA						NLTHA					
	Beams		Columns		Struts		Beams		Columns		Struts	
	Yield	Ultimate	Yield	Ultimate	Yield	Ultimate	Yield	Ultimate	Yield	Ultimate	Yield	Ultimate
BC1	40	0	20	0	80	60	0-20	0	0-16	0	60-75	17-60
BC2	44	0	0	0	57	57	16-44	0	0-4	0	35-57	3-50
BC3	66	0	6	0	75	75	0-58	0	0-6	0	0-68	0-18
BC4	61	0	14	0	50	50	0-38	0	0-4	0	50-53	12-46
BC21R2H	33	0	4	0	14	7	33	0	4-14	0	42-46	0-25
BC 2 2R	27	0	9	0	17	7	27-33	0	14-19	0	28-42	14
BC 2 3R	22	11	23	0	10	7	16-27	0-11	14-19	0	0-14	10-14
BC 2 3H	27	0	0	0	28	14	22-50	0	0	0	35-60	3-42
BC31R2H	41	0	0	0	12	0	0-58	0	0-13	0	0-62	18-25
BC 3 2R	33	0	0	0	12	6	0-41	0	0-20	0	0-56	18-25
BC 3 3R	41	16	33	0	18	12	16-33	0-8	20-26	0	0-12	0-6
BC 3 3H	66	0	0	0	37	31	0-66	0	0	0	0-75	0
BC41R2H	44	0	0	0	25	12	11-44	0	0	0	50	9-46
BC 4 2R	27	0	23	0	25	12	0-27	0	0-9.5	0	0-40	0-25
BC 4 3R	27	0	19	0	21	12	0-27	0	0-19	0	0-31	0-21
BC 4 3H	44	0	0	0	25	12	0-44	0	0	0	0-50	0-46

Fig. 5. Comparison of response spectrum of IS 1893 and seven ground motions.

- (a) The maximum inelastic drift (Δ_{CM} from NLTHA) is always greater than PP of NLPoA. Almost all the buildings have yielded under MCE, thus NLPoA highly underestimates the response.
- (b) Yielding in beams is less in BC1 (0-20%) compared to BC2, BC3 and BC4 (0-58%); however, a greater number of columns yielded in BC1 (0-16%) compared to BC2, BC3 and BC4 (0-6%). This implies that building on slopes without changes in the boundary condition perform better than building on plain ground considering the smallest height in calculating the natural period.
- (c) Overall, the yielding of beams is less in BC4 with changes in boundary condition (0-44%) compared to BC2 and BC3 buildings (0-58%) with no failure in beams except BC2 3R and BC3 3R with 0-11% and 0-8% ultimate failure of beams.
- (d) The failure in struts is very high in all the buildings reaching a 75% yielding and 60% ultimate failure. This implies that struts increase the stiffness of the buildings save the building from failing under MCE. But all together they will behave like a bare frame building without having influence of struts which may lead to catastrophic failure.

Fig. 6. (a) Damages in beams and columns due to yielding NLTHA GM3; (b) Ultimate failure of beams and columns NLTHA GM3

Conclusions

Buildings constructed on hill slopes have shown more vulnerability in the event of an earthquake and their failure in past earthquake have led to huge loss of human lives and property. Additionally, these buildings face perpetual vulnerability to potential landslides, risking the partial or complete compromise of their foundation rigidity. Further different configurations of buildings on slope behave differently in the event of an earthquake. Thus, it is necessary to understand the performance of different building configurations with changes in their boundary conditions in the event of an earthquake. In this parametric study 2D MRF buildings with varying boundary conditions are checked for their performance on the basis of equivalent static, response spectrum, NLPoA and NLTHA. The following are the observations made in the study:

1. For building on uniform ground greater than 80% mass participation is achieved whereas it reduces for buildings on slope depending upon the type of configuration ranging between 54% to 72%. Also varying building configuration changes the buildings natural period on software compared to code based calculated natural period as the code-based expression does not account different parameters that could affect the building natural period and its performance in the even of an earthquake.
2. Under nonlinear static analysis BC2 buildings with changes in boundary condition underperformed compared to BC3 and BC4. BC21R2H and BC23R have very less inelastic drift less than 1% which implies that the energy dissipation capacity of these buildings is very less. At PP yielding in beams ranges between 22% to 66% with no failure in beams in most of the buildings except BC2 3R and BC3 3R which are having 11% and 16% failure of beams. Failure of beams are occurring in place where the only two supports are present implying complete failure of these buildings.
3. Under MCE level of shaking damage level in struts have reached 75%. Overall, the yielding of beams is less in BC4 with changes in boundary condition (0-44%) compared to BC2 and BC3 buildings (0-58%); there is no failure in beams except BC2 3R and BC3 3R, which are having 0-11% and 0-8% ultimate failure of beams. BC4 is better suited in the event of changes in boundary conditions than BC2 and BC3.
4. Though various critical parameters are identified, only limiting height may not sustain the earthquake effects. It is necessary to study the influence of other critical parameters (especially including soil structure interaction)

in detail before placing the restrictions on building codes. Further detailed study shall be performed in 3D buildings before providing the design recommendations.

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